

Pottery shape descriptions

Collection of terms used by English native speaker pottery experts to describe the shape of pottery discovered during archaeological excavations in the eastern Mediterranean and dating to the Hellenistic and Roman periods. These terms were used to improve the translation of German pottery descriptions to English and the basis for the other files in this package. Numbers refer to the catalog number of the object.

L. Cornell – S. Herbert – A. Berlin – K. Warner Slane, *Tel Anafa. II: 1, The Hellenistic and Roman Pottery*, *Journal of Roman Archaeology. Supplementary Series 10: II,1* (Ann Arbor MI 1997)

- table amphora: medium-sized, two-handled jar with a base (rather than a toe) and a wide neck and mouth
 - angled rim, ridged strap handles, plain neck, wheel-ridged globular body, narrow folded ring foot (PW 1-5)
 - concave rim (PW 6-7)
 - double rim (PW 8-9)
 - everted ledge rim with groove on top
- lagynoi (42): table jugs with specific characteristics of a long, slim neck, vertical strap handle, and carinated or biconical body
 - folded lip (PW 18-20)
- table jug (48): single handled pouring vessels in a size and fabric suitable for serving, rather than kitchen, use.
 - folded
 - rim (PW 38-42)
 - banded rim (PW 43-45)
- table juglet (50): small, single handled pouring vessels, made of more finely levigated plain ware, with a smoother finish; utility juglets made of rougher ware
 - stumpy foot (49-52) – Persian juglet; thickened, rolled rim – “mushroom” rim
 - flanged rim (PW 59-62)
- amphoriskoi (54): all small jars with two handles; narrow-necked and footed vessels thought to have been used as miniature oil flasks
- unguentaria (58): any vessel designed to hold unguents; modern terminology connotes a specific shape: a vessel with a narrow mouth, long neck, bulbous body, and no handles
 - fusiform (PW 99-106): tall and slender
 - piriform (PW 11-116): pear shaped body
- ointment pot
- bowl
 - incurved rim (PW 133-140): general small, between 4 and 6 cm high and 11 to 18 cm in diameter
 - everted rim (PW 141-144): generally small and consistent in size, about 5 or 6 cm high and 15 cm in diameter
 - “Koan-Knidian” bowl (PW 149)
- saucer: small, shallow saucers with a central depression and surrounding ridge
 - spatter ledge rim (PW 150-155): narrow horizontal ledge rim, turned crisply off a wide, shallow, smooth-walled body. Between 18 and 21 cm in diameter

- spatter grooved rim (PW 156-159): wide, shallow body and slightly thickened rim with a broad groove circling the interior. Between 20 and 22 cm in diameter
- saucer-lids:
 - single folded rim (PW 162)
 - double folded rim (PW 163-167)
 - hooked rim (PW 168-170)
 - squared rim (171-172)
 - rounded rim (173-175)
- cook pot
- casserole(94): open cooking vessel, generally applied to shaper wider than they are tall; characteristics: lip shaped to carry a lid, rounded or angular body wall, more or less rounded bottom
 - grooved rim (PW 229-233): shallow body and wide ledge rim with a narrow groove near the outer edge
 - angled rim (PW 234-40): shallow body and plain, upwardly angled rim
 - beveled lip (PW 241-47): wide rim, angled upwards, with a sharp flange at the interior wall juncture and a neatly beveled lip
 - squared lip (PW 248-253): fairly deep, with straight, thick, wheel-ridged walls, and a round bottom; a high rim curves up and out from the body, the lip is roughly thickened into a small square
 - offset rim (PW 254-258):

S. I. Rotroff, *Hellenistic Pottery: Athenian and Imported Wheelmade Table Ware and Related Material, Athenian Agora 29* (Princeton N.J. 1997)

Vessels for food service

- plate (142):
 - thickened edge (623-630)
 - rolled rim
 - rilled rim (776-815): small plate or saucer with a wide rim reserved and marked with two grooves
 - concave rim (816-819): heavy, convex wall; rim is horizontal or inwardly sloping, reserved, and usually slightly concave on top
 - offset rim (838-848)
 - upturned rim (847-853)
- saucer (149): saucer or deep plate
 - projecting rim: sometimes called plate but never as flat or shallow as that term implies
 - downturned rim (743, 745, 746)
 - ridged rim (751)
 - angular wall (743)
- large plate/serving platter
- bowl
 - outturned rim (866-959)
 - vertical upper wall (960-964)
 - echinus bowl – incurved rim
 - beveled bowl (1037-8)
 - footed hemispherical bowl (1039-1044): inwardly beveled rim and a widely spreading foot

created by Nicole High-Steskal, September 2017

- projecting rim (1045-1049)
- deep bowl; projecting rim (1090-1105)

cooking stand